

Participatory tools

WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE & HOW

REFLECTING ON THE PARTNERSHIP: BUILDING A BALANCED PARTNERSHIP AND WIDER NETWORKS

How to identify and connect with other networks (other projects and their network)?

The project (all participants and stakeholder groups) needs to be connected as closely as possible to existing networks. Connections allow it to be improved and challenged by other skills, knowledge etc. and maximise future impact through the influence and mobilization of the other networks once the project begins to produce outputs.

How to solve it

It helps if the individuals and organisations are involved during the preparation phase of the project to identify potential networks.

Contributors who have already worked together know each other and understand how they work. This saves precious time (both for the creation of the project and for relationship building) and facilitates the project's progress.

However, these internal linkages do not allow for, or at least do not encourage, the renewal of working methods and networks, nor do they allow for the diversification of bottom-up issues. The sharing of knowledge

is, therefore, more limited. So, you have to find a balance between building a project where all the partners know each other and a project where none of the partners knows each other; while controlling diversity and covering the knowledge and skill needs for the project (see "How to form a well-balanced consortium?").

You can designate a person responsible for links with other networks to manage this task. Throughout the project, this person will ensure a "watch" (to create links with new networks) and share information and results with the other networks.

Word of advice

It helps to anticipate the time needed for this essential but time-consuming investment in the project.

Targeting the networks or people who will enrich the project, who will assist in meeting the project's objectives, will help disseminate the results. They can even participate in the project

To involve multiple networks in a project, it is advisable to plan a meeting of the networks (or their representatives) and the

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

project partners at the beginning to define the objectives of the relationship, the role of the participants, and the "rules" (regularity of meetings, types of information shared, etc.). This approach will lend even more importance to the networks and can only be beneficial for disseminating results.

Don't just stick to your usual networks if you need new skills and a fresh eye on the topic. Do not hesitate to seek out partners with whom you are not used to working. As long as they are motivated, the cooperation will only be more enriching.

You can invite external partners and internal actors to sign the confidentiality rules of the project. Those who do not sign it can nevertheless be informed of the project, but they cannot be internal actors.

How to form a well-balanced consortium (in terms of geography, skills, experience etc.)? / How to involve relevant actors?

This question deals with the building of the consortium. The first step is identifying relevant actors and when the (first) contacts are made.

Diversity within a project is an asset and has been cited several times as a success factor in multi-actor projects "the complementary skills of project partners and the good cooperation between project partners" (Protecow, LTR). This diversity can be geographical (different languages, cultural contexts etc.), functional (researchers, advisors, farmers, etc.), experiential (various degrees of experience of participation in research projects, on technical themes, community-building etc.). Everyone will bring their knowledge, skills, vision, and experience from their context.

Diversity (especially geographical diversity) can hinder the smooth running of the project and, therefore, innovation. Indeed, the more diversity there is, the more time and effort it will take to translate and establish a common language.

How to solve it

Care should be taken to find the balance between too much and too little diversity. A small core team is often more efficient than large working groups.

It is not skills that "work", but individuals. Moreover, people will collaborate with each other on the one hand and with the coordinator on the other. The "soft skills" of the individuals are essential. "The personality is really the key" (Inno4Wood). It is important to have effective complementary skills in scientific and technical fields, but also in the types of activities (research, translation, experimentation, etc.). The person behind the skills is essential.

Word of advice

If possible, you can choose the people, their soft skills, in addition to their technical skills. A project is a team.

To face the challenge of language differences, you can designate someone to be in charge of the translation can help. Patience is required.

If there is a lack of skills or knowledge, it is quite possible to ask for outside help without this person (a broker, a facilitator, etc.) being a full-fledged actor in the project.

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

The challenge for governance is to create cohesion between people from different backgrounds. Until the team has reached a significant level of cohesion, it tends to be only a collection of individuals with little to share.

Bringing together actors with complementary skills helps. If specific skills are indispensable and rare (carried by only one person), you can - if possible – think of a backup plan, with another person(s) being able to make up for the absence/disappearance of the first person.

One example of a tool to facilitate these stages

What, Who, Why, Where, When & How - « Brainstorming of Who should be involved? Who should be around the table? »

Description of the tool (see Impact assessment handbook in LIAISON toolbox)

- **What:** plan multi-actor tasks in advance, challenge multi-actor consortia with implementing multi-actor tasks in a rigorous and meaningful way, plan at the level of the whole-project/initiative how the project intends to engage with its actor/stakeholder community to avoid fatigue
- **How long:** 1-2h
- **How many:** Whole multi-actor group, small to large. Particularly useful for large consortia who are challenged with coordinating a consistent multi-actor approach across many tasks
- **What you'll need:** sticky notes, markers

Steps:

- Explain the purpose, logic and background
 - **What:** The facilitator writes a 'topic banner,' i.e. a title on flip chart paper – 'What MAA Tasks?' Starting from the beginning of the project and working through to the end, participants are facilitated to identify all tasks in the project/initiative that employ the MAA.
 - **Who:** The facilitator writes a 'topic banner,' i.e. a title on flip chart paper – 'Who should be involved in this MAA Task?' (taking each task in turn, with its own flip chart paper). Participants identify, for each task, the actors (who should be involved as partners) and the stakeholders (who should be consulted).
 - **Why:** actors are invited to identify why actors/stakeholders may be motivated/incentivised to participate in the tasks. Why, from their perspectives, are they likely to want to be involved? Each actor & stakeholder type is taken in turn for each task, and a motivations register is built.
 - **Where and When:** At this step in the process, the logistical questions of "where"? And "when"? are answered, specifically about the events/activities of the project, involving actors and/or stakeholders. They are

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

addressed together, particularly for international projects/initiatives, as there may be possibilities to hold more than one activity/event together (for stakeholder engagement, for example).

Testimony of the use

Aine Macken-Walsh, sociologist, Teagasc, Ireland

This tool, often used by Aine Macken-Walsh in project facilitation, is "very useful to help the facilitator and the participants think critically about who should be involved in the tasks".

It helps to address different questions:

- What: What is the task to be done?
- Who: Who should be involved?
- Why: Why do these actors want to be involved? "This is perhaps the most important question to understand: why do these stakeholders want to be involved in the project? What would be their motivation for getting involved in the project? The facilitator needs to understand the stakeholders' point of view to understand their interest in being involved in the project. The reason why a farmer would want to be involved in a particular project is completely different from that of a researcher."
- Where: logistical issue
- When: a question of logistics

"The very design of this tool aims to raise awareness and make people more aware of the needs and motivations of others".

